

Gre Virike: Early Bronze Age Cultic Installations

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Entry tags: Mesopotamian Religions, Religious Group, Near East, North Mesopotamia, Mesopotamian Religion, Early Bronze Age, Religious Place, Middle Euphrates, Mesopotamia

Gre Virike is located on the east bank of the Euphrates River, about 10 km north of the Turkey-Syria border. Rescue excavations at Gre Virike were undertaken within the Salvage Project of the Archaeological Heritage of the Ilisu and Carchemish Dam Reservoirs in Turkey. Excavations at the site were conducted by Prof. Dr. A. Tuba Ökse under the auspices of the Şanlıurfa Museum. The center was built on a gravel terrace ca. 10 km north of the ancient city of Carchemish. The high temple terraces that arose in Mesopotamia during the 4th millennium BC were built on natural hills or mounds in Northern Mesopotamia due to the rugged terrain. On some of the terraces dating to the 3rd millennium BC, monumental chamber tomb complexes were built overtop of temple architecture and open-air ritual spaces. The high terrace built on Gre Virike is represented by water, incense, and sacrifices in the first half of the 3rd millennium BC, and by monumental burial complexes in the second half of the 3rd millennium BC. In the Middle Euphrates basin, both high terraces and monumental tombs exist together. The fact that these ritual areas, which are seen in the Middle Euphrates basin and established at intervals of 18-20 km on average, are at such distances that people living in the surrounding rural settlements can return to their destination within the same day, suggests that these areas may have been built for rural settlements. When the dimensions of the labor and materials used in the construction of the terraces are calculated, the existence of an influential political structure in the region emerges in this period. It is understood that the rich people belonging to the kingdom at Ebla, which dominated the region west of the Euphrates River, may have ruled these rural areas and that the monumental chamber tombs belonging to these people were built in these ritual areas. The rulers gained a different status in the religious field by performing the rituals in these tomb complexes.

Date Range: 3000 BCE - 2000 BCE

Region: Şanlıurfa Region

Region tags: North Mesopotamia

This region covers an area between the Birecik-Karkamış Dam lakes in the Middle Euphrates Basin.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In these buildings, there are kitchens for the ceremonial meal, and within the framework of the cult of fertility, saplings were grown, the water of the nearby spring and sacrifices were offered to the gods, and the ceremonial meal was eaten. The fact that Gre Virike was founded on the Euphrates and is not located in a settlement is reminiscent of the location of Akitu temples in Mesopotamia. In this context, there may be a relationship with the god of fertility.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ökse, A. Tuba. "Early Bronze Age Chamber Tomb Complexes at Gre Virike (Period IIA) on the Middle Euphrates" 339 (August 2005): 21-46. <https://doi.org/10.1086/basor25066901>.
- Source 2: Ökse, A. Tuba. "Early Bronze Age Graves at Gre Virike (Period II B): An Extraordinary Cemetery on the Middle Euphrates" 65, no. 1 (January 2006): 1-37. <https://doi.org/10.1086/504902>.
- Source 3: Ökse, A. Tuba. "Gre Virike (Period I): Early Bronze Age Ritual Facilities on the Middle Euphrates River." *Anatolica* 32 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.2143/ANA.32.0.2012551>

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Grain and leguminous seeds and animal bones left in the graves at Gre Virike seem to be associated with the cult of the dead. However, the food remains found outside the tombs show that the food for the dead was eaten during the commemoration ceremonies.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Pre-modern

↳ Years of excavation:

–Year range: 1999-2002

↳ Name of excavation

–Official or descriptive name: Gre Virike

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The terrace construction must have taken 4 or 5 months with at least 100 people. The size of the graves and the quality and number of grave goods indicate that these graves were made by the elite.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know this as there are no written documents available.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: In Mesopotamian written sources, it is stated that food and drink were served to the dead in order for the soul of the dead to find peace, and that food was eaten at funerals and commemoration ceremonies. Gre Virike is an example of this.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Ökse, A. Tuba. "Early Bronze Age Chamber Tomb Complexes at Gre Virike (Period IIA) on the Middle Euphrates" 339 (August 2005): 21-46. <https://doi.org/10.1086/basor25066901>.

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– Source 3: Ökse, A. Tuba. "Gre Virike (Period I): Early Bronze Age Ritual Facilities on the Middle Euphrates River." *Anatolica* 32 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.2143/ANA.32.0.2012551>

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Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

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Type of excavation:

– Pre-modern

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1999-2002

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Gre Virike

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Field doesn't know

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In these buildings, there are kitchens for the ceremonial meal, and within the framework of the cult of fertility, saplings were grown, the water of the nearby spring and sacrifices were offered to the gods, and the ceremonial meal was eaten. The fact that Gre Virike was founded on the Euphrates and is not located in a settlement is reminiscent of the location of Akitu temples in Mesopotamia. In this context, there may be a relationship with the god of fertility.

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

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Notes: Grain and leguminous seeds and animal bones left in the graves at Gre Virike seem to be associated with the cult of the dead. However, the food remains found outside the tombs show that the food for the dead was eaten during the commemoration ceremonies.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The terrace construction must have taken 4 or 5 months with at least 100 people. The size of the graves and the quality and number of grave goods indicate that these graves were made by the elite.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

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Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

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Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: In Mesopotamian written sources, it is stated that food and drink were served to the dead in order for the soul of the dead to find peace, and that food was eaten at funerals and commemoration ceremonies. Gre Virike is an example of this.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– No

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The monumental tomb complexes on the high terrace at Gre Virike are interrelated structures.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The quality and abundance of the items found in some graves indicate the existence of elites and thereby a hierarchy.

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
–Percentage: 60

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
–Square meters: 50

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
–Height, meters: 3

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
–Square meters: 150

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
–Height, meters: 2

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
–Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Field doesn't know

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably the clay from the Euphrates River was used as a source.

↳ Wood

– Field doesn't know

↳ Grass

– Field doesn't know

↳ Stone

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It was probably procured from the immediate surroundings of the center.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Ground stone tools were found as building material on the tomb walls.

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The monumental tomb complexes on the high terrace at Gre Virike are interrelated structures.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

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– Percentage: 60

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 50

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 3

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 150

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 2

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Field doesn't know

↳ Clay

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↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably the clay from the Euphrates River was used as a source.

↳ Wood

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↳ Grass

– Field doesn't know

↳ Stone

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It was probably procured from the immediate surroundings of the center.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Ground stone tools were found as building material on the tomb walls.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It has been known that comparable terraces and monumental chamber tombs were constructed along the riverside in the Middle Euphrates basin, with distances ranging from 18-30 kilometers. As a result, it is proposed that nearby rural communities would have likely visited these holy sites for ritualistic reasons. Given these findings, it appears plausible that individuals residing in rural settlements could reach these sacred locations on foot within a few hours.

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: It was a common belief in the ancient Near East that if offerings were not made to the souls of the deceased, they would suffer and become angry with the living. As a result, individuals would frequently leave food and water on graves as a way of honoring the dead. Similar rituals were also conducted in this place.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: This is difficult to predict

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: It is likely that it is done at the start of every new farming season.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We only know that incense is burned during ceremonies.

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: It's possible that the foot bones found in a grave near the wall corner at Gre Virike belonged to an animal that was sacrificed and then placed on top of the grave. This type of practice was also common in prehistoric Europe.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is a ritual center for celebrating the start of the new agricultural year and holding ceremonies for the dead.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Field doesn't know

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: This is evident in both tombs and structures associated with them, such as canals

and sacrificial pits.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It was a common belief in the ancient Near East that if offerings were not made to the souls of the deceased, they would suffer and become angry with the living. As a result, individuals would frequently leave food and water on graves as a way of honoring the dead.

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Jewelry and personal ornaments are available.

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

Notes: Two 0.1 mm thick gold leaf decorations were found in the mud-brick cist grave.

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that miniature vessels were utilized for rituals, while high-stemmed bowls functioned as altars.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Family members of the deceased often placed food and drinking vessels in their relatives' graves as part of their burial customs. However, ritual objects such as toys, figurines, masks, terra-cotta models, musical instruments, bells, and candles were rarely included. It was common to find beds, matting, sarcophagi, and ceramic vessels in which the deceased had been laid.

↳ Other

–Yes [specify]: Family members of the deceased often placed food and drinking vessels in their relatives' graves as part of their burial customs. However, ritual objects such as toys, figurines, masks, terra-cotta models, musical instruments, bells, and candles were rarely included. It was common to find beds, matting, sarcophagi, and ceramic vessels in which the deceased had been laid.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although there were instances of reuse and secondary burials, no evidence of maintenance was discovered in these structures.

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is a ritual center for celebrating the start of the new agricultural year and holding ceremonies for the dead.

For the worship of a deified human:

– Field doesn't know

For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Jewelry and personal ornaments are available.

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

Notes: Two 0.1 mm thick gold leaf decorations were found in the mud-brick cist grave.

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– Yes

Notes: It is believed that miniature vessels were utilized for rituals, while high-stemmed bowls functioned as altars.

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– Other [specify]: Family members of the deceased often placed food and drinking vessels in their relatives' graves as part of their burial customs. However, ritual objects such as toys, figurines, masks, terra-cotta models, musical instruments, bells, and candles were rarely included. It was common to find beds, matting, sarcophagi, and ceramic vessels in which the deceased had been laid.

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Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It was a common belief in the ancient Near East that if offerings were not made to the souls of the deceased, they would suffer and become angry with the living. As a result, individuals would frequently leave food and water on graves as a way of honoring the dead.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: It was a common belief in the ancient Near East that if offerings were not made to the souls of the deceased, they would suffer and become angry with the living. As a result, individuals would frequently leave food and water on graves as a way of honoring the dead. Similar rituals were also conducted in this place.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: This is difficult to predict

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: It is likely that it is done at the start of every new farming season.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We only know that incense is burned during ceremonies.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: It's possible that the foot bones found in a grave near the wall corner at Gre Virike belonged to an animal that was sacrificed and then placed on top of the grave. This type of practice was also common in prehistoric Europe.

Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although there were instances of reuse and secondary burials, no evidence of maintenance was discovered in these structures.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It has been known that comparable terraces and monumental chamber tombs were constructed along the riverside in the Middle Euphrates basin, with distances ranging from 18-30 kilometers. As a result, it is proposed that nearby rural communities would have likely visited these holy sites for ritualistic reasons. Given these findings, it appears plausible that individuals residing in rural settlements could reach these sacred locations on foot within a few hours.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:
 - Yes [specify]: This is evident in both tombs and structures associated with them, such as canals and sacrificial pits.

Are festivals present:

- No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

- Field doesn't know

Notes: Gre Virike appears to have no connection with any particular settlement in close proximity. It is suggested that the chamber tombs placed on the high terraces were organized by the elites. However, there is uncertainty regarding the existence of a structured bureaucracy in this situation.

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

- No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

- Field doesn't know

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: There are other structures associated with the tombs. However, it is clear that these structures were not used as living spaces.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: There are other structures associated with the tombs. However, it is clear that these structures were not used as living spaces.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Gre Virike appears to have no connection with any particular settlement in close proximity. It is suggested that the chamber tombs placed on the high terraces were organized by the elites. However, there is uncertainty regarding the existence of a structured bureaucracy in this situation.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Gre Virike: Early Bronze Age Cultic Installations, Ökse, A. Tuba. "Gre Virike 1998 Araştırması / Gre Virike Research in 1998.". In *Ilisu Ve Karkamış Baraj Gölleri Altında Kalacak Arkeolojik Kültür Varlıklarını Kurtarma Projesi 1998 Yılı Çalışmaları* (pp. 119-155), edited by N. Tuna and J. Öztürk. Ankara: Ortadoğu Teknik Üniversitesi, 1999.

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